

THE ROLE OF THE STATE SECURITY SERVICE BODY IN PUBLIC AND SOCIAL LIFE

Qo'chqorov Anvarjon Vakiljon o'g'li

*Student of the Faculty of Jurisprudence, Andijan Institute of Agriculture and
Agrotechnologies*

E-mail address: anvarjonqochqorov59@gmail.com

Annotation: You will learn more about the State Security Service, a law enforcement agency, in this article. It will also highlight the main functions of this body, its legal status, how important it plays in society and public life in upholding human rights and freedoms, and what responsibilities the body has. Most importantly, the State Security Service relies on what policy-making frameworks in its hierarchy.

Keywords: State Security Service, Armed Forces, Soviet Socialist Republic of Uzbekistan, law-enforcement agency, president, sovereignty, terrorism, extremism, organized crime, initial investigation, investigation, infringement, committee.

Аннотация: В этой статье вы узнаете больше о Службе государственной безопасности, правоохранительном органе. Также будут освещены основные функции этого органа, его правовой статус, насколько важную роль он играет в обществе и общественной жизни в отстаивании прав и свобод человека, какие обязанности возложены на этот орган. Самое главное, что Служба государственной безопасности опирается на то, какие политические рамки в ее иерархии.

Ключевые слова: Служба государственной безопасности, Вооруженные силы, Советская Социалистическая Республика Узбекистан, правоохранительный орган, президент, суверенитет, терроризм, экстремизм, организованная преступность, досрочное расследование, следствие, нарушение, комитет.

The concept and history of the State Security Service body in our independent state

The State Security Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the law-enforcement and supervisory bodies that are part of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

On September 26, 1991, according to the decree of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, the State Security Committee of the UzSSR KGB was transformed into the National Security Service. The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers for the transformation of the State Committee DX into the NSC, November 2, Killingan. In the decision, it is noted that the number of sick people will be taken by 25% in Holda, which received the liquidated individual divisions of the State Committee.

On March 18, 2018, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev issued a decree on reforming the bodies of the National Security Service. According to him, on March 29, 2018, by the decision of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the name of the organization was changed to the State Security Service. April 5 was designated as the professional holiday of service personnel. On August 24, 2021, by the decision of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the DXX profession holiday was moved to September 26. The following are the main tasks of the DXX:

The State Security Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan is designated as a special authorized body protecting the constitutional system, sovereignty, territorial integrity and interests of the Republic of Uzbekistan from external and internal threats.

The service protects the state security and interests of the Republic of Uzbekistan from external and internal threats.

In this area, it will carry out activities to strengthen legality and the rule of law, to prevent violations, to identify them and to put an end Performs intelligence and counterintelligence activities to prevent, identify and eliminate encroachments on the constitutional system, sovereignty and territorial integrity of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Guards and protects the state borders of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Fight against terrorism, extremism, organized crime, illegal trafficking of arms, narcotics and psychotropic substances; conducts activities to prevent, identify and eliminate subversive activities aimed at promoting national, racial and religious enmity that threaten the interests and security of the state.

Ensures state security in the economic, scientific-technical, social and informational spheres. Protects the historical, cultural and rich spiritual heritage of the people of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Fights against corruption in state bodies and other organizations that threaten the interests and security of the state, ensures state security in the field of

telecommunications and transport, prevents, identifies and eliminates factors that cause emergency situations.

Controls the preservation of state secrets, security of special communication and organization of cryptographic protection of information in state bodies and other organizations.

Performs tasks such as identifying and eliminating the causes and conditions that make it possible to commit offenses that threaten the interests and security of the state.

Chairmen of the State Security Committee of the USSR:

1. Bizov Alexey Petrovich (April 20, 1954 - February 11, 1960);
2. Georgiy Fedorovich Naimushin (February 26, 1960 - December 14, 1963);
3. Kiselev Sergey Ivanovich (December 14, 1963 - October 25, 1969);
4. Beschastnov Alexey Dmitriyevich (October 25, 1969 - October 25, 1974);
5. Nordman Eduard Boleslavovich (October 25, 1974 - March 2, 1978);
6. Melkumov Levon Nikolayevich (March 2, 1978 - August 24, 1983);
7. Vladimir Aleksandrovich Golovin (August 24, 1983 - January 27, 1989);
8. Anatoly Sergeevich Morgasov (February 23, 1989 - June 12, 1991);

Chairman of the National Security Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

1. Gulam Aliyevich Aliyev (June 12, 1991 - June 27, 1995); [7]
2. Inoyatov Rustam Rasulevich (June 27, 1995 - January 31, 2018);

Heads of the State Security Service:

1. Abdullayev Ikhtiyor Bakhtiyorovich (January 31, 2018 - February 11, 2019);
2. Azizov Abdusalam Abdumavlonovich (February 11, 2019).

The importance of regulatory legal documents in the activity of the State Security Service.

As long as we are talking about the State Security Service, it is our duty to emphasize the legal norms that are important in its activity. First of all, the law "On the State Security Service" defines the main activities of this body, its main tasks, the legal status of the body and, of course, what responsibilities are assigned at the legal level, as well as the limits of its authority. In particular, the main tasks of the State Security Service are mentioned in Article 2 of the law. The main tasks of the State Security Service are to protect the constitutional system, sovereignty, territorial integrity and other state interests of the Republic of Uzbekistan from external and internal threats, to strengthen legitimacy and ensure the rule of law, as well as to prevent, identify and prosecute violations of the State Security Service. is to terminate. Article 5 of the law defines the legal status and main directions of

activity of the State Security Service. The state security service is a specially authorized state body that carries out its activities with special means, forms and methods in order to ensure state security.

The State Security Service implements a unified state policy in the field of state security and operates in the following main areas within its powers:

- Ensuring the state security of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the protection of state interests from external and internal threats, strengthening legality and the rule of law in this area, preventing violations, identifying them and ending them;
- Carrying out intelligence and counter-intelligence activities to prevent, identify and eliminate encroachments on the constitutional system, sovereignty and territorial integrity of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- Guarding and protection of the State border of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- Participation in the implementation of strategic initiatives to protect the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the defense-industrial complex from threats and threats to state security, to strengthen the country's defense capabilities;
- fight against terrorism, extremism, organized crime, illegal trafficking of arms, narcotics and psychotropic substances;
- prevention, detection and suppression of subversive activities aimed at promoting national, ethnic and religious enmity that threaten the interests and security of the state;
- ensuring state security in the economic, scientific-technical, social and information spheres, protecting the cultural-historical and rich spiritual heritage of the people of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- fight against corruption in state bodies and other organizations that threaten the interests and security of the state;
- ensuring state security in the field of telecommunications and transport, preventing, identifying and eliminating factors that create conditions for emergency situations;
- investigation and pre-investigation of criminal cases included in the competence of the State Security Service, carrying out preliminary investigations, conducting rapid search activities;
- control over the preservation of state secrets, security of special communication and organization of cryptographic protection of information in state bodies and other organizations;

- to identify and eliminate the causes and conditions that make it possible to commit crimes that threaten the interests and security of the state;
- Improving and maintaining the combat and mobilization readiness of the State Security Service, preparing forces and means for action in case of emergency situations and the introduction of martial law.

In addition, based on the normative legal document No. PF5379 adopted on March 14, 2018, the name of the National Security Service was changed to the State Security Service. was entrusted. In particular, the law stipulates that the flag of the State Security Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan should have the appearance of a dark blue rectangular fabric, which represents stability, fortitude, loyalty, dedication and courage, and a heraldic symbol in the center of the flag - The emblem of the State Security Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the flag of the State Security Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan should be 250 cm long and 125 cm wide.

Conclusion: At the end of our speech, we should emphasize that the main task of all law enforcement agencies is to ensure human rights and freedoms, the main task of the State Security Service is to protect human rights and freedoms, is to prevent violations of legal documents established by the state. In this article, the concept of the State Security Service, the main directions and tasks of the body's activity, as well as its historical evolution, as well as its reliance on and implementation of a number of normative legal documents in its activities, were explained.

References:

1. The newest history of Uzbekistan Matyokubov H.H. 2021.
2. Presidential Decree on Measures to Improve the State Security System of the Republic of Uzbekistan March 14, 2018.
3. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Security Service" April 5, 2018.
4. History of Uzbekistan Qamariddin Usmanov 2006.
5. Abdurahmanova, M., & Raxmanova, A. (2021). Корпус Лингвистикасида Полисемия. Computer Linguistics: Problems, Solutions, Prospects, 1(1).
6. Israilova, S., & Alavutdinova, N. (2023). Intercultural Color Interpretation. Science and innovation, 2(C12), 111-115.
7. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Security Service" April 5, 2018.
8. Turapovna, I. S. (2021). Semantics of the lexeme "green". ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(9), 440-448.

9. Abdurahmanova, M. (2021). Legal Fundamentals of Land Resources Of Usance To Achieve Economic Efficiency. Экономика и финансы (Узбекистан), (Спецвыпуск 4), 187-189.
10. Turdievna, K. Z., & Tursunalievna, A. M. (2023). Problems of Understanding and Translating Homonyms in the Artificial Intelligence System. International Journal of Language Learning and Applied Linguistics, 2(5), 63-67.
11. Tursunaliyevna, A. M. (2021, August). Occasionalism and Their Artistic and Aesthetic Functions. In " Online-Conferences" Platform (pp. 19-23).
12. Presidential Decree on Measures to Improve the State Security System of the Republic of Uzbekistan March 14, 2018